

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.	B499		
Date:	20/1/10		
Take Off:	11:12:29Z	Z	Z
Landing:	16:41:34Z	Z	Z
Flight Time:	5h 29m5s	h m s	h m s

Campaign: CONSTRAIN

Operating Area: North Sea / North West Scotland

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 2	Keith Bower	Manchester Uni
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry / AVAPS training	Angela Dean	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	FAAM
8	CVI	Paul Barratt	Met Office
9	CVI/Mission Scientist Training	Kirsty McBeath	Met Office
10	Mission Scientist 1	Richard Cotton	Met Office
11	Mini-LIDAR	Franco Marengo	Met Office
12	Manchester Cloud	James Dorsey	Manchester Uni
13	SID3	Edwin Hirst	Uni Herts
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			

	Log Sheet included
Y	Flight Folder Front Page
Y	Flight Summary
	Met Office 0600 UTC Actual Surface analysis (ASXX) chart
Y	Track Plot (GIN or GPS)
	DFLFliteStar planned track
Y	Brief
	Mission Scientist 1's logs
	Mission Scientist 2's logs
	De-brief
	ViRC chat log
	Flight Manager's Instrument Status log
Y	Flight Manager's Faults/Incidents log
Y	Pre-flight log
Y	Core Chemistry / NOx / TDLAS
Y	Cloud Physics In Flight
	Cloud Physics Processing
	AVAPS
	PSAP log
	Filters
	Printed Plots
Y	Screengrabs (Weather Radar)
	Planning charts or plots
	Images Emailed To BAe146 In Flight

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	2010-01-20	Alan Woolley	Initial version
R1			
r2			

10:50:51 – 16:43:25

GLon_PARA0611, GLot_PARA0610

B499 20 January 2010 CONSTRAIN Flight 4

Sortie S8: Ice nucleation in super-cooled Stratocumulus

Super-cooled Stratocumulus with cloud tops reaching -10°C makes an ideal case study for heterogeneous ice nucleation.

Weather

Sortie location

North sea, just off northeast coast between Aberdeen and Newcastle.

Operate between fixed ground points

A: $56^{\circ}\text{N } 1^{\circ}40\text{W}$

B: $56^{\circ}50\text{N}, 2^{\circ}\text{W}$

C: $56^{\circ}\text{N}, 0^{\circ}10\text{E}$

D: $55^{\circ}20\text{N}, 1^{\circ}20\text{W}$

Sortie summary

Observe Stratocumulus by a series of straight and level runs along fixed ground points.

Sortie detail

- 1) **Transit** to operating area at best-range speed and altitude, arriving at point **A**.
- 2) **Profile descent:** along **B** to **A**, from 10kft through cloud layer to 50ft, to estimate cloud top and base.
- 3) **Profile ascent:** along **A** to **D**, from 50ft to 2000ft above cloud top.
- 4) **Lidar run:** Perform straight and level 2000ft above cloud top.
- 5) **Cloud penetration runs:** Perform straight and level runs, just above cloud top, just below cloud base and in-cloud. Check for icing of turbulence probe during in-cloud run.
- 6) **Precipitation run:** Perform straight and level run 500ft below cloud base.
- 7) **Saw-tooth run:** between 1000ft above cloud top and 500ft below cloud base.
- 8) If region of high precipitation observed during in-cloud run, break-off and do extra runs in cloud.
- 9) **Return transit** at best range speed.

Instrument requirements

Lidar operated to identify cloud base. No varying integration time or changing the display.

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B499

Date: 20/1/10

Project:CONSTRAIN

Location:Prestwick

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
110038		startup	0.07 kft	075	
110531		taxy	0.07 kft	061	
110651		asp open	0.07 kft	069	
111229		T/O	0.05 kft	120	Prestwick
112136	115657	Run 1	9.0 kft	345	
115658	121302	Profile 1	9.0 - -.09 kft	092	
120056		descent rate	5.4 kft	093	500ft/min
120940		qnh 1016	1.4 kft	093	
121302	122823	Profile 2	-.09 - 8.0 kft	098	
123129	125839	Run 2	8.0 - 7.9 kft	282	
125844	130218	Profile 3	7.9 - 5.3 kft	265	
130223	131556	Run 3	5.3 kft	090	
131602	132030	Profile 4	5.3 - 0.96 kft	093	
132043	132241	Run 4	0.94 - 0.97 kft	091	
132246	132425	Profile 5	0.89 - 0.12 kft	094	
132432	132543	Run 5	0.15 - 0.12 kft	097	
132548	132835	Profile 6	0.12 - 2.8 kft	092	
133121	135414	Run 6	2.9 kft	094	
135415	135606	Profile 7	2.9 - 4.0 kft	262	
135821	141328	Run 7	4.0 - 3.9 kft	087	
141328	141924	Profile 8	3.9 - 0.12 kft	092	
141924	142352	Run 8	0.12 - 0.21 kft	092	
142352	142528	Profile 9	0.21 - 2.1 kft	350	
142528	144352	Run 9	2.1 - 1.5 kft	255	
144623	144928	Profile 10	1.6 - 0.00 kft	126	
144928	150429	Run 10	0.00 - 0.03 kft	093	
150429	151035	Profile 11	1.7 - 6.2 kft	137	
151120	152339	Run 11	5.6 kft	271	
152339	152818	Profile 12	5.6 - 0.98 kft	269	
152825	153541	Run 12	0.95 - 0.16 kft	094	
153542	154146	Profile 13	0.20 - 6.0 kft	092	
154355	154936	Profile 14	5.9 - 1.1 kft	273	
154936	155839	Profile 15	1.1 - 10.0 kft	266	

155839	162751	Run 13	10.0 - 9.9 kft	294
164134		Land	-.01 kft	121 Prestwick

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B499

Date: 20 Jan 10

Instruments

1. Nevz TWC only
- 2.

Aircraft

- 1.

Satcom

MPDS –

Satcom H –

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) $\frac{1}{4}$ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Supercooled - STRATO CUMULUS.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B499** Date 20/1/10 Name R. COTTON Page 1 of 1

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	P camp on	CVI	reports	COMMS	problem prior to loop close.
	all other	don't	phys	operating	(will try and re-start PLAP trans)
	use SID 2	for	aerosol	run?	
	* increase	TRIG/GAIN	levels.		Take-off Cranwick, 111229
	for	low-level	run.		overcast, no rain.
					pass through low cloud during climb
		6000ft	in	cloud	cir 100 obs large aggregates.
111800					Tc = -7.5°C in cloud
112115	R1st	FLO90			In cloud CO does CAL
1134		FLO90	in	dry layer	out of cloud Tc = -12°C Td = -26°C
					8/8 Sc below, 9/8 Ci/As above
	(Sc top)	climb out high	~ -5°C	Li	far cloud top 5000 - 5500
1146		* as expected	Just off	const. 56° 6, 242	Ci breaking - p ~ 4/8 Ci
1154		ahead	expect	illp, to	each Ci much less.
115659	R1st	FLO90			Tc = -9.5°C.
120030		5800ft.			Cloud top Tc = -3.7°C
	some	in	build	up.	nice fall streaks ahead! Tc = -8°C now?! Td = -6°C
					Cloud base
	Sea	obs	occasi	n/3000ft	Tc: -4°C Td: -4°C thinning.
	Raged	back			Cloud base ~ 2000ft Tc = -2°C
					no precip observed 1016 WNH
	CO	sees	some	ice!!	Mostly water.
	def/	super	cooled	Sc.	
121302	P1st	Soft.			
121302	P2st	Soft			Tc: 4°C Td: -2°C

-3

~16min.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B499** Date Name **R. Cotton** Page **1** of **5**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Cloud base -2°C, Top -8°C
121430		800ft			8/8 Sc above.
		2200			Cloud base Tc: -3°C Td: -5°C
122344		5400ft			cloud top Tc: -9°C Td: -9°C
		some isol. peaks ~6000ft			0/8 Ci off overhead.
		Turbulence probe		Flight manager says ok but winds differ from aircraft.	
122820	P2end		start	turn	procedural.
123121	R2st	8000ft		LIDAR run	0/8 Ci Tc: -8.5°C Td: -19°C above at eastern end
		~25 min	Run.		strong inversion at cloud top. 4-6°C CO also has step change Tc: -8°C Td: -22°C
1245		800ft			Becoming overcast. 4/8 Ci, but still in clear/dry air. 8/8 Sc below.
125835	R2end	8000ft.			Profile descent during procedural turn.
130223	R3st.	5400ft			aim run alt = 5500 ft, may nudge few times descent further to begin climb 5300ft now 5400ft.
					visually near top. Tc: -9°C, Td: 8°C
130502					just out cloud briefly nudge to 5500ft. 2000 ice on cylinders
131325		just out			of cloud
131550	R3end	need to descend			for de-icing.
132025	R4st.	1000ft			de-icing run.
		251ft			"
					Not science run.

LIDAR run
≈ 27 min

LIDAR at 6050, 5800, 5700, 5650, * may need to nudge aircraft alt. east pressure alt. from trough. west/land 1616 QNH is dark-enough.

Mission Scientist's Log

300m
 8 min short or ~20 min runs

Flight No **B.49.1.** Date Name **R. Coates** Page **3** of **8**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	will	shorten	runs	just	proc turn, and do cloud base.
132135		2900ft		ascend	to cloud base to re-start science.
132121	R6st	2700ft			westbound.
					pt 56N, 5500E
		80°	kinetic	heath	
1340		2 hours duration left *			Tc: -4°C, Ta: -2°C
1340		cloud probe			sometimes operating
134905		near base			occasionally (obs sea)
134905		direct			slightly to go thru inc in green return
		increase			is low. Not much ice build up at this time
135410	Rent	Maybe			just nearer base at westward end.
		4000ft.			in cloud run
		CP reports			increased ice fractions.
135818	R7ot	4000ft.			ice seen on pylon. Tc: -6°C, Ta: -5°C
140125					lean port side pylon.
140720		angle of attack			sensor on turbulence probe?
141220	R7end	2030m			ice on pylons descend to deposit.
					Cloud base. 2700ft
		Precip run			2200ft. Turb probe still not giving there.
141924	R8st.				Tc: -2°C Ta: -2°C next C 56N, 150E
					cloud base is variable, but we are below.
					1600ft. Tc: -0.3°C, Ta: -1°C
142920					CP 100 now seeing larger particles
144307					observe more precip?
144352	R9end				1600ft

1340
 1540
 4 runs left

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B479** Date Name **R. Cotton** Page **4** of **5**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
144728	R _{st} ¹⁰	100ft			Low level research runs
1450	500ft Precip	windscr	194825		8/8 Sc above.
145255		more double	on	windscr.	interfaded with other radar returns.
1457		wind	1949	at 110°	Tc = 4.2°C Td = -1.7°C
		PCASP		decreases	from 900 to 400 during this run.
150400	R ₁₀ ^{rent}	100ft			Cloud base ~ 1700ft.
				as we turn,	can see Sc is becoming more broken.
					Cloud top 5700ft.
151119	R ₁₁ st	5600ft			in cloud top
				in and out of top occasionally	
				X	Tc = -10°C, Td = -10°C
1514			10min	port	polygon.
1517			20-5	gone	
1518			20min	port	polygon
152337	R ₁₁ ^{ent}				increase to 5800ft, dec to 5600ft.
	R ₁₂ st	100ft			default run - X Not science X
		time	for	3 profiles	
					waiting for 2D-5 and last in to go for polygon
153545	R ₁₃ ^{ent}	200ft.			could not wait for 2D-5 because of ATC.
					ATC request 600ft max alt.
					2/pci over head - some mid level clouds, but dry layer as in Sc
154140	not sure	when	Parent	was on track,	so do Parent straight

avg re. top Tc = -10°C 5900ft

Cloud top
run
5500ft

1514

Cloud Physics Flight Log B499

Date:17/01/2010	Operator: MAP	DRS Time:09:00:00	DAU1 Time:same	DAU2 Time:same	AUX1 Time:same	AUX2 Time:same
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DAU2 Disk space?

	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		CIP-15		SID2+SID3		2DC	
Operated?	Y		Y		Y		Y		Y		y	
Pre-flight checks	Ref V:	3.04	Vref (>7V):	5.38	El#1 V (>1):	1.16	El#1 V (>1):	2.9	Comms2?:	y	El#1 V (>1):	-2.4
	Data TX?	Y	Sample flow	1.21	El#32 V (>1):	2.4	El#32 V (>1):	3.1	Comms2?:	Y	El#32 V (>1):	-2.1
			Sheath flow	14.09	El#64 V (>1)	1.28	El#64 V (>1)	3.2				
			Spectra ok?	Y								

Just after take-off	Are SAMPLE and RECORD buttons on PADS both green?	y	Are all heaters on? (Check ammeters and CIP dummy box heater switch).	Y
	Are all PADS instruments enabled and updating?	y		

NOTE that CTRL+T will insert the current time where the cursor is as long as the cursor is a cursor and not a selected box.

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R			
08:51:16			15	U/S								PCASP voltage too low
08:54:25			30									
08:56:30			40									
11:21:30	FL090											Start Run 1
11:22:00		0.1	40					12	800	8	10	
11:24:00								5	800	8	5	
11:26:00						0.01		17	800	8	5	
11:28:00						0.005		25	800	8	3	
11:30:00												
11:34:00						0.01		9	800	8	1	
11:38:00		0									0	
11:40:00		0									0	
11:42:00		0									0	
11:44:00		0									0	
11:46:00		0									0	
11:48:00		0									0	

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R			
11:50:00		0									0	
11:52:00		0									0	
11:54:00		0									0	
11:56:00		0									0	
11:56:54	FL090	0									0	End of Run & Start Profile 1
11:57:59	FL080	0									0	
11:59:06	FL070	0									0	
12:00:14	FL060	0									0	
12:01:38	FL050	50	17			0.001		21	400	1	10	
12:03:45	FL040	70	15			0.002		320	200	1	2500	
12:05:58	FL030	5	15			0.001		75	200	1	10	
12:08:19	FL020	0				0.001		45	200	1	1	
12:10:21	FL010	0				0.0005		25	300	1	0.01	
12:13:01	50'	0									0	End of Profile 1 & Start Profile 2
12:15:00	FL010	0				0.0002		1		1	0	
12:17:06	FL020	0				0.0004		2	600	8	10	
12:19:00	FL030	0.6	30			0.0002		11	300	1	1000	
12:20:55	FL040	3	15			0.0002		14	500	1	2000	
12:22:50	FL050	25	15			0.0002		10	300	1	2000	
12:24:39	FL060	0									0	
12:26:33	FL070	0									0	
12:28:17	FL080	0									0	End of Profile 2
12:31:22	FL080											Start Run 2
12:32:00		0									0	
12:34:00		0									0	
12:36:00		0									0	
12:38:00		0									0	
12:40:00		0									0	
12:42:00		0									0	Change in LWC (pitot iced up?)
12:44:00		0									0	
12:46:00		0									0.01	
12:50:00		0									0.01	
12:52:00		0									0	
12:54:00		0									0	
12:56:00		0									0.01	
12:58:40	FL080											End of Run & Start Profile 3

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R			
12:59:52	FL070	0									0	
13:00:55	FL060	0									0	
13:02:24	FL052											End of Profile & start Run3
13:03:00		75	17			0.0004		25	500		2250	
13:05:00	FL054	120	17			0.0002		70	400		1000	
13:07:00		150	19			0.0001		120	325		1250	
13:09:00		140	19			0.0001		1000	400		750	
13:11:00		170	19			0.0001		10	500		300	
13:13:00		130	19			0.0001		1	500		1000	
13:15:00		140	18			0.0001		1			1000	
13:15:59												End of Run & Start Profile 4
13:17:22	FL040	120	14			0.002		160	200		250	
13:19:23	FL020											
13:20:34	FL010											End of Profile & Start Run 4
13:21:00	FL010	0						Noise?			0	
13:22:42								Run off	????			End of Run & Start Profile 5
13:24:25	250'											End of Profile 5 & Start Run 5
13:25:00		0									0.1	
13:26:46												End of Run & Start Profile 6
13:26:45	FL010	0									200	
13:28:36	2500'											End of Profile
13:31:16	FL028											Start Run 6
13:32:00		0.1	15			0.004		6	700	8	1	
13:34:00		2	20			0.0005		1	700	8	200	
13:40:00		2.5	20			0.0005		8	700	8/1	200	
13:42:00		2.5	17			0.0004		2	700	8	200	
13:44:00		2.5	18			0.0005		15	500	8	600	
13:46:00		10	15			0.0005		20	700	1	800	
13:48:00		7	18			0/0005		6	400	1	10	
13:50:00		5	18			0.0004		20	325	1	200	
13:52:00		2	20			0		3	700	8	1	
13:54:15	FL028											End of Run 6 & Start Profile 7
13:56:06	FL040											End of Profile
13:58:20	FL040											Start Run 7
13:59:00		70	15					20	700	1	1200	
14:01:00		70	15			0.001		25	550	1	2000	

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R			
14:03:00		100	15			0.001		40	550	8	2000	
14:05:00		100	15			0.001		25	550	8	1700	
14:07:00		100	15.5			0.004		130	350	1	1750	
14:09:00		100	14.7			0.001		25	275	1	1500	
14:11:00		90	14.5			0.0003		60	400	1	1800	
14:30:24												End of Run & Start Profile 8
14:14:27	FL030	4	15			0.0001		25	200	1	200	
14:15:55	FL020							Noise				
14:17:50	FL010							3	800	1	200	
14:19:20	250'											End of Profile & Start Run 8
14:20:00						0.0001		1	800	1		
14:22:00						0.0001		1				
14:23:46	250'											End of Run & Start Profile 9
14:24:32	FL010					0.0002		2	800	1	0.2	
14:25:28	FL021											End of Profile & Start Run 9
14:26:00		0.03	20			0.0005		10	800	1	0.3	
14:28:00	FL017					0.0002		10	575	1	1	
14:30:00	FL015	0.02	15									
14:32:00		0.01	15			0.0005		1	500	1	0.1	
14:34:00		0.01	15			0.0001		1	500	1	0.1	
14:36:00		0.01	15			0.0001		2	700	1	0.1	
14:38:00		0.01	10			0.001		4	800	1	0.4	
14:40:00		0.01	10			0.0005		3	600	1	0.3	
14:42:00						0.0005		2	600	1	0.1	
14:43:55												End of Run
14:46:23	FL015											Start Profile 10
14:49:26	250'											End of Profile & Start Run 10
14:50:00		0.04	10									
14:52:00		0.04	10									
14:54:00		0.04	10			0.0001		1	400	1	0.1	
14:56:00								0.5				
14:58:00						0.0001						
15:00:00												
15:02:00		0.02	45			0.0001					0.1	
15:04:32	250											End of Run & Start Profile 11
15:05:35	FL010	0.02	40								0.1	

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R			
15:06:32	FL020	0.5	40			0.001		6	800	1	250	
15:07:41	FL030	0.5	45			0.001		18	350	1	1800	
15:08:38	FL040	45	15			0.001		23	400	1	2200	
15:09:30	FL050	90	19			0.001		15	600	1	200	
15:10:44	FL062	0										End of Profile
15:11:21	FL055											Start Run 11
15:12:00		120	19								250	
15:14:00		160	20			0.0001		?			500	
15:16:00		160	20			0.002		Noise?			1200	
15:18:00		160	20			0.002		?			1700	
15:20:00	FL057	140	16			0.0005		?			250	
15:22:00	FL055	100	19			0.0001		?			1000	
15:23:35	FL055											End of Run & Start Profile 12
15:25:27	FL040	60	15									
15:26:16	FL030					0.0002		?				
15:27:30	FL020					0.0002		?			0.1	
15:28:16	FL010											End of Profile & Start Run 12
15:29:00						0.0001		?			0.1	
15:31:00	250					0.0001						
15:33:00						0.0001		1	500	1	0.1	
15:35:00		0.1	15									
15:35:40	250'											End of Run & Start Profile 13
15:36:26	FL010					0.0001		5	800	1	0.1	
15:37:31	FL020					0.0001		3	600	1	0.2	
15:38:15	FL030	0.2	25			0.0005		8	550	1	600	
15:39:17	FL040	9	17			0.0005		8	200	1	2000	
15:40:24	FL050	70	18			0.0001		4	100	1	1200	
15:41:17	FL060											End of Profile
15:43:55	FL060											Start Profile 14
15:44:54	FL050	130	15			0.0001		15	700	1	200	
15:46:05	FL040	80	15			0.0001		10	200	1	1000	
15:47:15	FL030	20	15			0.0005		2	550	1	1	
15:48:27	FL020					0.0005						
15:49:37	FL010					0.0001		6	800	1	1	End of Profile & Start Profile 15
15:50:45	FL020					0.005		3	800	1	10	

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R			
15:51:45	FL030					0.015		30	700	8	500	
15:52:50	FL040	10	16			0.003		40	600	8	1500	
15:53:50	FL050	80	17			0.002		20	300	1	2250	
15:54:50	FL060											
15:55:47	FL070											
15:56:45	FL080							Noise				
15:57:33	FL090							Noise				
15:58:37	FL100											End of Profile

Post flight

Instrument	Diagnostics		Brief report on instrument performance
PCASP (od)	Vref:		N/A
	Flow:		
2DC	EI#1:		
	EI#32:		
PCASP SPP-200	Ref V:	5.2	Reference Voltage too low
	Flow:		
CDP	Laser V:	3.42	
FFSSP	Ref V:		N/A
SID 3	Laser V:		
Rack Equipment			

B499 20/1/10

In-Flight CO Calibrations

Please log fluorescence cell temperature and pressure immediately following calibration. During warm cabin flights, temperature can reach 40°C. During flight levels >FL020, cell pressure will drop (down to 5.9 at FL030)

		Nominally 66 Hz/ppbv	Nominally 34000 Hz	Nominally 7.5 Torr	Nominally 35 - 40 °C
Time	Flight level	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbv)	Background Count (Hz)	Cell Pressure (Torr)	Lamp Temp (°C)
01/18/2010 17:00:37	Previous Flight	65.143	32840.60	N/A	N/A
01/18/2010 ~11:00	Pre-Flight/Gnd	See notes	See notes	See notes	See notes
01/20/2010 11:35:40 see note	9.0kft	65.049	34137.90	7.54	35.51
01/20/2010 12:44:30	8.0kft	64.508	33773.54	7.54	36.08
01/20/2010 13:16:11	5.3kft	63.835	33462.63	7.51	36.94
01/20/2010 13:33:46 (run interrupted)	0.15kft	63.751	33591.23	7.50	37.17
01/20/2010 13:44:27	2.9kft	63.695	33408.33	7.56	37.39
01/20/2010 14:38:28	2.1kft	63.624	33317.33	7.54	37.76
01/20/2010 15:41:18	1kft	63.150	33077.40	7.51	38.38
01/20/2010 16:25:57	10kft	63.320	33115.80	7.53	38.43
Time	Flight level	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbv)	Background Count (Hz)	Cell Pressure (Torr)	Lamp Temp (°C)

Pre-Flight & In-Flight comments/faults report

CO Monitor averaged zero (either in Hz or ppbv) : last zero: 01/20/2010 11:35:40 34137.90.
 NOx monitor averaged zero (ppbv) : _____
 Ozone Monitor averaged zero (ppbv) : _____

CO Calibrations on automatic repeat? : /NO Interval set? : 40 mins

Science power shut off at some point during security due to GPU problem. Re started at ~10:45. O3/NOx clean air check and CO Zero were both in progress during this time. Instrument restarted and zeros restarted. Zero continued during taxi, ended remotely by flight manager before take off. FM also did cal on ground - but I started the 1st in flight cal BEFORE details off the on ground cal was copied over. **Oops. Sorry!**

Observation: The 1st in-flight cal hyperterminal call confirms lastcal at 11:35:40. It was actually more like 11:21.36, which was when the first run began. Is this time correct?
 2nd cal - 12:32 (not 12:44)...

Data for averages during Zero check:
 NOx ppb: -0.01, -0.02, -0.07, -0.16, -0.23, -0.23, -0.29, -0.30, -0.27, -0.19
 O3 ppb: 0.9, -1.8, -1.9, 0.2, -1.5, -1.2, -0.2, 0.1, -1.2

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date:

Flight No: **B 494**

Pre-Flighter: **SC**

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
1	✓	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
2	✓	Core Chemistry	Enter cyl content press	CO N₂ N ₂ = 145 bar CO₂ Ar = 65 bar
3	✓	Core Chemistry	Driers OK	
4	✓	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
5	✓	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
6	✓	Core Chemistry	All Flows Checked OK	
7	✓	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
8	✓	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
9	✓	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
10	✓	HORACE	Recording data	
11	✓	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
12	✓	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
13	✓	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
14	✓	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
15	✓	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
16	✓	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	
17	—	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	not fitted
18	✓	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
19	✓	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
20	✓	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
21	—	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
22	✓	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
23	✓	Satcom C	Checked	In cockpit
24	✓	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
25	—	CNC	Butanol filled	
26	—	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	
27	—	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	
28	—	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	
29	—	3786 CPC	DI Checked / Topped up	u/s.

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
30	—	CCN Water	Supply filled / Drain empty	
31	—	CCN SS cols A & B	Set to manual A0.2, B0.1	
32	—	CCN Pressure	Normally set to 650mb	
33	—	CCN Flow Ratios	A & B = 10 ± 0.3	
34	—	3786 CPC	Drained	
35	—	CPC Laptop	AIM Software set up	
36	✓	Core Chemistry	O ₂ /NO _x /CO zeros performed	Ok
<u>External Checks</u>				
37	✓	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
38	✓	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
39	✓	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
40	✓	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
41	✓	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
42	✓	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
43	✓	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
44	x	WAS Bottles	No. fitted and position.	
45	✓	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
46	✓	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
47	✓	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
48	✓	All other covers	Removed	
49	✓	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol!**
50	—	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
51	—	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u> <u>Signed</u>				
52	✓	Upper BBRs	Checked & Cleaned	
53	✓	ICEX	applied	
54	✓	Turb Probe - Traps	emptied, detail contents -	a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more

Range: 320
Tilt: +0.00
Gain: Min
Stand-by

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ents\weather radar\CONSTRAIN WX

Go

	Size	Type	Date Modified	Date Pict
1 59 01.png	8 KB	PNG Image	18/01/2010 11:59	
1 58 31.png	8 KB	PNG Image	18/01/2010 11:58	
1 58 01.png	8 KB	PNG Image	18/01/2010 11:58	
1 57 31.png	8 KB	PNG Image	18/01/2010 11:57	
1 57 01.png	8 KB	PNG Image	18/01/2010 11:57	
1 56 31.png	8 KB	PNG Image	18/01/2010 11:56	
xRx2010 01 18 11 56 01.png	8 KB	PNG Image	18/01/2010 11:56	
xRx2010 01 18 11 55 31.png	8 KB	PNG Image	18/01/2010 11:55	
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Folders

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Name	Size	Type	Date Modified	Date Pict
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xRx2010 01 18 12 14 31.png	8 KB	PNG Image	18/01/2010 12:14	
xRx2010 01 18 12 14 01.png	8 KB	PNG Image	18/01/2010 12:14	
xRx2010 01 18 12 13 31.png	8 KB	PNG Image	18/01/2010 12:13	
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xRx2010 01 18 12 10 31.png	8 KB	PNG Image	18/01/2010 12:10	
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xRx2010 01 18 12 09 31.png	8 KB	PNG Image	18/01/2010 12:09	
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xRx2010 01 18 12 08 31.png	8 KB	PNG Image	18/01/2010 12:08	
xRx2010 01 18 12 08 01.png	8 KB	PNG Image	18/01/2010 12:08	
xRx2010 01 18 12 07 31.png	8 KB	PNG Image	18/01/2010 12:07	

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Go

Bluetooth

Flight data

My Music

My Pictures

My Videos

SnagIt Catalog

Updater5

weather radar

b459wxrx.dat

DAT File

65,412 KB

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80 160 240 320

Range: 320
Tilt: +0.00
Gain: Min
Stand-by

Power adapter detected in the docking station. The dock will be disabled and your system will operate on battery power. Please connect the power adapter or higher to the dock for best system operation.

OK

Range: 320
Tilt: +0.00
Gain: Min
Stand-by

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OK

Range: 320
Tilt: +0.00
Gain: Min
Stand-by

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Range: 320
Tilt: +0.00
Gain: Min
Stand-by

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Tilt: +0.00
Gain: Min
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Range: 320
Tilt: +0.00
Gain: Min
Stand-by

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Tilt: +0.00
Gain: Min
Stand-by

Power adapter detected in the docking station. The dock will be disabled and your system will operate on battery power. Please connect the power adapter or higher to the dock for best system operation.

OK

80 160 240 320

WINDSHEAR

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

Test

Power adapter detected in the docking station. The dock will be disabled and your system will operate on battery power. Please connect the power adapter or higher to the dock for best system operation.

OK

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

Power adapter detected in the docking station. The dock will be disabled and your system will operate on battery power. Please connect the power adapter or higher to the dock for best system operation.

OK

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

Power adapter detected in the docking station. The dock will be disabled and your system will operate on battery power. Please connect the power adapter or higher to the dock for best system operation.

OK

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

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OK

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

Power adapter detected in the docking station. The dock will be disabled and your system will operate on battery power. Please connect the power adapter or higher to the dock for best system operation.

OK

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

Power adapter detected in the docking station. The dock will be disabled and your system will operate on battery power. Please connect the power adapter or higher to the dock for best system operation.

OK

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

Power adapter detected in the docking station. The dock will be disabled and your system will operate on battery power. Please connect the power adapter or higher to the dock for best system operation.

OK

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

Power adapter detected in the docking station. The dock will be disabled and your system will operate on battery power. Please connect the power adapter or higher to the dock for best system operation.

OK

1

3

4

5

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

Power adapter detected in the docking station. The dock will be disabled and your system will operate on battery power. Please connect the power adapter or higher to the dock for best system operation.

OK

1

3

4

5

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

Power adapter detected in the docking station. The dock will be disabled and your system will operate on battery power. Please connect the power adapter or higher to the dock for best system operation.

OK

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

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Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

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Gain: Max

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OK

1 3 4 5

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
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